

BOOK of ABSTRACTS

International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing

**2nd International Conference
on Advanced Production and Processing
20th-22nd October 2022
Novi Sad, Serbia**

Title:

Book of Abstracts of the 2nd International Conference on Advanced Production and Processing publishes abstracts from the following fields: Innovative Food Science and Bioprocesses, Nutraceuticals and Pharmaceuticals, Sustainable Development, Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Materials Design and Applications, Petroleum Refining and Production.

Publisher:

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

For publisher:

prof. Biljana Pajin, PhD, Dean

Editorial board:

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Editor-in-Chief:

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Design and Printing Layout:

Saša Vulić

CIP - Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteke Matice srpske, Novi Sad

658.5(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL Conference on Advanced Production and Processing (2 ; 2022 ; Novi Sad)
Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / 2nd International Conference on Advanced Production and Processing, 20th-22nd October 2022, Novi Sad ; [editor-in-chief Zita Šereš]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Technology, 2022

Način pristupa (URL): <https://www.tf.uns.ac.rs/download/icap-2022/book-of-abstracts.pdf>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 14. 10. 2022. - Nasl. s naslovnog ekrana.

ISBN 978-86-6253-160-5

a) Tehnologija - Proizvodnja - Apstrakti

COBISS.SR-ID 77341961

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VARIABILITY OF MICROCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE HAUSNER RATIO AND COMPRESABILITY INDEX DEPENDING ON DETERMINATION METHODOLOGY

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Microcrystalline cellulose is a powder commonly used in pharmaceutical technology as filler in tablet and capsule formulations. Flowability is an important characteristic of powders, because it affects quality of final pharmaceutical dosage form in terms of adequate dosing and therefor therapeutic effect. Hausner ratio and Compressibility index are measures of powder compressibility used to express powder flow characteristics. The aim of this study was to determine effect of graduated cylinder volume and filling mass of Hausner ratio and Compressibility index. In this study 3 graduated cylinders of different volume were used: 10 ml, 100 ml and 250 ml. Each cylinder was firstly filled with microcrystalline cellulose up to 1/3 of its capacity, then 1/2 and finally 2/3. Jolting volumeter was used to determine bulk and tapped volume of each powder mass in all of the 3 tested cylinders. Measurements were done after 10, 500, 900 and 1250 strikes. Compressibility index and the Hausner ratio were calculated based on the obtained results, according to 10th European Pharmacopoeia. Statistical tests (ANOVA) were performed with SPSS[®] program and the differences were considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$.

Both Hausner ratio and Compressibility index were shown to be statistically significantly different when measured in graduated cylinder of 250 ml between 1/3 filling and 1/2 as well as 1/3 and 2/3. In graduated cylinder of 100 ml, statistically significant difference was observed between 1/3 filling and 2/3, and 1/2 and 2/3. In graduated cylinder of 10 ml, there was no statistically significant difference among different amounts of cylinder filling. When filled up to 1/3 of volume capacity, no statistically significant difference of examined flowability parameters was observed between cylinders of 250 ml and 100 ml. For 1/2 and 2/3 of filled capacity, no statistically significant difference was observed between cylinders of 250 ml and 10 ml. Difference between pharmacopoeial description of flowability was observed for all three tested cylinders and between tested fillings. Depending on methodology used, the tested powder flowability could be considered either Poor, Very poor or Very, very poor.

Hausner ratio and Compressibility index were shown to depend on determination methodology and therefor results obtained by different methodology can't be considered comparable. Although for the small volume cylinder no statistically significant difference of flowability parameters between filling amounts was determined, difference in pharmacopoeial description is still observed.

Keywords: Flowability, Powder, Microcrystalline Cellulose, Flowability Parameters.

Acknowledgements: This study was supported by The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia [number 451-03-68/2022-14/200114].